

Derivation of the Einstein's Mass-Energy Equation from the Newton's Second Law of Motion

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Abstract: In the Einstein's theory of special relativity, the relativistic mechanics is concerned with the motion of bodies whose velocities approach the speed of light. It is understood the velocity of a moving particle with non-zero mass is always less than the speed of light with zero mass. So, the speed of light is the upper limit for all moving objects in the universe. This paper presents an efficiency mass-energy equation instead of the Einstein's mass-energy equivalence.

Keywords: relativistic motion, momentum equation, kinetic energy, rest mass energy

1. Introduction

The Einstein's mass-energy equivalence [1-19] of an object with non-zero mass (m) is $E = mc^2$, where E is the sum of kinetic energy and rest mass energy and c is the speed of light. In the next section, the Einstein's mass-energy equation is derived from the Newton's second law of motion by differentiation and integration [10].

2. Efficiency Mass-Energy Equation

The Einstein mass-energy equivalence denotes the equation of relativistic energy. In the theory of special relativity, the relativistic momentum is concerned with the motion of a particle whose velocity approaches the speed of light.

The Newton's second law of motion states that the force (F) acting on a particle is equal to the rate of change of its momentum (p).

$$F = \frac{dp}{dt} = \frac{d(mv)}{dt}, \text{ where momentum } p = mv.$$

According to Einstein's relativity theory, mass (m) is a variable over time. By differentiating the force equation, we get

$$F = \frac{dp}{dt} = \frac{d(mv)}{dt} = m \frac{dv}{dt} + v \frac{dm}{dt}, \text{ where } v \text{ is velocity.}$$

The differential equation for work and kinetic energy is derived as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} dK &= dW = Fds \\ dK &= Fds = \left(m \frac{dv}{dt} + v \frac{dm}{dt} \right) ds \\ dK &= Fds = m \frac{ds}{dt} dv + v \frac{ds}{dt} dm, \text{ where } \frac{ds}{dt} = v \end{aligned}$$

Note that $K = \frac{1}{2}mc^2$, where c is the speed of light, and its differential equation $dK = \frac{c^2}{2} dm$.

$dK = mv dv + v^2 dm$, where dK is kinetic energy.

$$\frac{c^2}{2} dm = mv dv + v^2 dm$$

Let $w^2 = \frac{c^2}{2} dm$. Then, $w^2 dm = mv dv + v^2 dm$

$$\frac{dm}{m} = \frac{v}{w^2 - v^2} dv$$

$$\int_{m_0}^m \frac{dm}{m} = \int_0^v \frac{v}{w^2 - v^2} dv$$

$$[\ln(m)]_{m_0}^m = -\frac{1}{2} [\ln(w^2 - v^2)]_0^v$$

$$\ln m - \ln m_0 = -\frac{1}{2} \ln(w^2 - v^2) + \frac{1}{2} \ln w^2$$

$$\ln \frac{m}{m_0} = \frac{1}{2} \ln \frac{w^2}{w^2 - v^2}$$

$$\frac{m}{m_0} = \sqrt{\frac{w^2}{w^2 - v^2}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{w^2}}} \Rightarrow m = \frac{m_0}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{w^2}}}$$

$$m^2 = \frac{m_0^2}{1 - \frac{v^2}{w^2}} \Rightarrow m^2(w^2 - v^2) = m_0^2 w^2$$

$$m^2 w^2 - m^2 v^2 = m_0^2 w^2$$

By differentiating the equation with respect to time, we get

$$2mw^2 \frac{dm}{dt} - 2mv \frac{d(mv)}{dt} = 0 \Rightarrow w^2 \frac{dm}{dt} = v \frac{d(mv)}{dt}$$

$$\text{Here, } \frac{dE}{dt} = Fv = v \frac{d(mv)}{dt} = w^2 \frac{dm}{dt}$$

$$dE = w^2 dm$$

$$\int_0^K dE = \int_{m_0}^m w^2 dm$$

$K = w^2(m - m_0)$, where K is kinetic energy.

$$K = \frac{c^2}{2}(m - m_0).$$

Einstein's mass-energy equation (E) = Kinetic energy (K) + Rest mass energy (m_0c^2)

$$E = \frac{c^2}{2}(m - m_0) + m_0c^2 = \frac{1}{2}(m + m_0)c^2$$

Here, this is contradiction with the Einstein's mass-energy equation $E = mc^2$.

Therefore, $E \neq mc^2$.

We know that $mgh = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 = mas$ and total energy $= \frac{1}{2}mv^2 + \frac{1}{2}mv^2 = mv^2$,

where mgh is potential energy, mas is work done, and $\frac{1}{2}mv^2$ is kinetic energy [18, 19].

As a result, the Einstein's mass-energy equation of an object with non-zero mass (m), where the Einstein's mass-energy equation is equal to the sum of kinetic energy and rest mass energy, must be $E = mv^2$, where $v < c$.

3. Conclusion

In this paper, we have justified the Einstein's mass-energy equivalence ($E = mc^2$) is wrong and introduced an efficiency mass-energy equation. This new idea can enable the researchers to be involved further in the field of relativistic mass-energy.

References

- [1] Annamalai, C. (2024) Einstein's Special Theory of Relativity: A New Mass-Energy Equivalence. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4698089>.
- [2] Annamalai, C. (2023) Energy-Momentum Equivalence. *CoE, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2023-g6bcz-v4>.
- [3] Annamalai, C. (2023) Momentum-Velocity Equivalence. *CoE, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2023-g6bcz-v3>.
- [4] Annamalai, C. (2023) Energy-Work Equivalence. *CoE, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2023-lsh2m>.
- [5] Annamalai, C. (2023) Lorentz Factor and Time Dilation on the Special Theory of Relativity. *TechRxiv, IEEE*. <https://doi.org/10.36227/techrxiv.24297325>.
- [6] Annamalai, C. (2023) Upper Limit for the Energy of Motion. *CoE, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2023-xtxmg>.
- [7] Annamalai, C. (2023) A New Mass-Energy Equivalence from Lorentz Factor and Energy of Motion. *CoE, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2023-cbbq0>.
- [8] Annamalai, C. (2023) Momentum-Velocity Equivalence. *CoE, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2023-g6bcz-v2>.
- [9] Annamalai, C. (2023) Computation of Mass-Energy Equation from Lorentz Factor and Kinetic Energy. *CoE, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2023-6nlxv-v2>.

- [10] Annamalai, C. (2023) The Einstein's Mass-Energy Equivalence and the Relativistic Mass and Momentum derived from the Newton's Second Law of Motion. *CoE, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2023-ck6jr-v3>.
- [11] Annamalai, C. (2023) Upper Limits for Velocity, Momentum, and Energy of Motion. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4660185>.
- [12] Annamalai, C. (2023) Mass-Energy Equivalence: Light Energy. *COE, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2023-639kj>.
- [13] Annamalai, C. (2023) Upper Limits for Relativistic Energy and Momentum. *COE, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2023-d48fx>.
- [14] Annamalai, C. (2023) Einstein's Special Theory of Relativity: A New Mass-Energy Equation. *COE, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2024-0gzht>.
- [15] Annamalai, C. (2025) Notes on the Mass-Energy Equation related to the Speed of Light. *HAL, Centre pour la Communication Scientifique Directe*. <https://hal.science/hal-04787154>.
- [16] Annamalai, C. (2025) Proving the Potential Energy mgh is equal to the Kinetic Energy. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14936809>.
- [17] Annamalai, C. (2025) The Einstein's Mass-Energy Equivalence relating to Total Energy. *Cambridge Open Engage, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2025-szhwp>.
- [18] Annamalai, C. (2025) Derivation of the Einstein's Mass-Energy Equation (Sum of Kinetic Energy and Rest mass Energy) using Classical Mechanics. *Cambridge Open Engage, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2025-szhwp-v2>.
- [19] Annamalai, C. (2025) The Einstein's Mass-Energy Equation: Kinetic Energy ($\frac{1}{2}mv^2$), Potential Energy (mgh), and Work done (mas). *Cambridge Open Engage, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2025-szhwp-v3>.